

ASSESSING HOW JOB ROTATION AFFECTS EMPLOYEE RETENTION IN RIVERS STATE COMPANIES

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ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
<p>This study investigates the relationship between job rotation and employee turnover in food and beverage firms located in Rivers State, Nigeria. Adopting a cross-sectional survey design, the research collected primary data using a structured five-point Likert scale questionnaire. The study population comprised 1,120 employees, from which a sample size of 295 respondents was determined using Taro Yamane's formula. Hypotheses were tested using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient with the aid of SPSS version 23.0. The findings revealed a statistically significant relationship between job rotation and both voluntary and involuntary employee turnover. Specifically, effective implementation of job rotation was shown to influence retention, while poor or misaligned rotation practices contributed to employee exit. The study concludes that strategic job rotation can serve as a valuable tool for workforce stability when properly managed.</p>	<p>Job Rotation, Employee Turnover, Voluntary Turnover, Involuntary Turnover, Workforce Retention</p>

Introduction

In today's increasingly dynamic and competitive global business environment, employees are no longer perceived merely as tools of production or operational resources. Rather, they are now regarded as **strategic assets** and integral contributors to the formulation, execution, and success of business strategies (Kwenin, Muathe & Nzulwa, 2013). Human capital represents one of the most critical success factors in an organization's performance, growth, innovation capacity, and sustainability. Organizations that invest in acquiring, developing, and most importantly, retaining talented employees often outperform their competitors. Conversely, high levels of employee attrition can have far-reaching negative consequences that extend beyond workforce shortages to issues of customer dissatisfaction, reduced innovation, disrupted workflow, and increased operational costs. The importance of employee retention cannot be overstated in modern organizational practice. According to Meyer and Smith (2000), organizations that ensure employee satisfaction and retention simultaneously guarantee customer loyalty, internal knowledge continuity, and efficient succession planning. High retention rates often signal a healthy organizational climate and strong leadership practices, which in turn make the company more attractive to new talents. However, employee turnover—the rate at which employees voluntarily or involuntarily exit an organization—remains a persistent challenge that impacts organizational stability, morale, and

performance (Armstrong, 2006). A high turnover rate implies frequent disruptions, increased recruitment and training costs, and loss of organizational knowledge and culture.

In the context of Nigeria's food and beverage sector, which is part of the broader manufacturing industry, employee turnover has become a matter of growing concern. This sector is labour-intensive, customer-driven, and competitive, requiring skilled, committed, and stable human resources. Retaining employees, especially those with valuable experience, is therefore essential for operational efficiency and customer satisfaction. However, despite awareness of its significance, many organizations continue to experience high turnover rates, leading to challenges in sustaining productivity and achieving business objectives.

Understanding Employee Turnover and Its Drivers

Employee turnover is a multidimensional concept influenced by a range of organizational, personal, and environmental factors. These include leadership style, work environment, training and development opportunities, job satisfaction, compensation and benefits, performance management systems, and overall organizational culture (Izzack, 2010). The decision to leave or stay in an organization may stem from employee-related reasons, such as a desire for career advancement, personal development, or better remuneration elsewhere. It can also result from employer-related factors such as poor management practices, lack of recognition, unclear job roles, or absence of growth opportunities. In addition, external environmental factors, including economic conditions, industry trends, and labour market dynamics, can also affect turnover rates.

Organizations must pay close attention to the causes and consequences of turnover, as it holds implications not just for the human resource function but for the organization's long-term strategic direction. As Gadot (2007) observes, the loss of skilled employees affects innovation, customer satisfaction, and accumulated institutional knowledge—elements that are central to sustainable competitiveness. Moreover, replacing employees is not only disruptive but also cost-intensive, involving expenses in recruitment, onboarding, training, and reduced productivity during the transition period. Thus, reducing employee turnover and improving retention have become central human resource priorities in many industries.

Measuring Organizational Performance and the Human Factor

Performance measurement remains critical in assessing the health and progress of any organization. It allows stakeholders to evaluate how well the organization is achieving its objectives and identifies areas requiring improvement (Johnson, 2010). In this regard, the **Balanced Scorecard** has emerged as a holistic framework that enables organizations to track performance not just financially, but also from the perspective of internal processes, learning and growth, and customer satisfaction. It emphasizes the integration of organizational goals across different departments and levels, helping align employee performance with corporate strategy.

Importantly, employee behavior and performance directly influence organizational success across all these dimensions. As such, retaining employees who are competent, motivated, and aligned with the organization's vision contributes significantly to business excellence. Turnover, especially when frequent or poorly managed, introduces volatility that undermines strategic focus and execution. For these reasons, human resource professionals are constantly seeking effective strategies to manage and reduce employee turnover while enhancing engagement, development, and satisfaction.

Job Rotation: Conceptual Framework and Strategic Role

One such strategy that has gained prominence in recent years is **job rotation**. Defined as the systematic and planned movement of employees across different roles or departments within an organization, job rotation is designed to **enhance skill development, increase motivation, and reduce monotony** in the workplace (Dessler

& Varkkey, 2009). Through exposure to different tasks and work environments, employees are given the opportunity to broaden their competencies, understand cross-functional operations, and prepare for future leadership roles.

Leat (2007) and Campion et al. (1994) explain that job rotation not

Figure 1.1: Conceptual Framework of Job Rotation and Employee Turnover.

Source: Researcher’s conceptualization (2019).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical Foundation

The theoretical foundation or baseline theory for this research was drawn from the Job characteristics theory proposed by Hackman & Lawler (1971). The job characteristics theory was formulated as a model of job redesign. According to Hackman & Oldham (1974, 1980) it was subsequently revised the job characteristics theory and termed their refinement the job characteristics model, hence forth referred to as model, which is now considered the most influential model guiding research on the nature or characteristics of jobs. Hackman & Oldham (1975) also developed a measuring instrument to validate their model, namely the job diagnostic survey (JDS), which was revised parallel to refinements of the model.

This model proposed action steps for improving motivation, satisfaction and performance and have been functionally utilized as a revised job redesign practice to address critical human resources problems currently facing managers and human resource practitioners. The model is underpinned by the humanistic management approach which purpose is to preserve, maintain and develop the human dynamic in the workplace. Job characteristic model and the job and job diagnostic survey were formulated and compiled for the explicit purpose of job redesign efforts in industry. From the above expression of the researchers, it is clear that the theory has a strong connection with job design and employee turnover in an organization.

Employee Turnover

Employee turnover is defined as the individual movement of employees across the membership boundary of organizations. This definition refers to employees moving into or out of an organization. According to Abbasi & Hollman (2000) has argued that from the perception of human resources management and organizational behavior, employee turnover is the rotation of employees around the labor market, that is, between firms, jobs, occupations and between the states of employment and unemployment. Alarape (2008) reported that organizations seek to retain highly productive and competent employees in order to improve organizational

effectiveness. He noted that, sometimes employees are disengaged from the organizations for several reasons. Employee turnover can be advantageous in such a way that opportunities are provided for the organization to lose its less productive employees. This in turn results to the recruitment of newly and highly productive employees, hence, gaining human capital value in addition to saving cost for the organization. Costs that could be incurred by the organization is separation cost, replacement cost and retraining costs. The loss of skilled, relevant and talented employees could stagnate organizational performance and productivity.

Voluntary Turnover

However, voluntary turnover of employee in an organization occurs as a result of the employee willingness to quit or separate himself from the firm. It could be resignation with an intention for alternate job, career development and intention to quit that current job. Voluntary Turnover Noe (2006), argued that when employees leave organizations at their own discretion, it is referred to as voluntary turnover. It is initiated by the choice of an employee. A related definition is given by Egan (2005), stating that an instance of voluntary turnover reflects an employee's decision to leave an organization, whereas an instance of involuntary employee turnover or a discharge reflects an employer's decision to terminate the employment relationship.

Involuntary Turnover

Thus, this kind of employee's turnover termed movement of an employee across the boundary of the organization at the discretion of the employer who decides to terminate the employment relationship. Voluntary turnover could be death, compulsory retirement, retirement due to age, economic adversity, inflation time etc. Involuntary Turnover according to Booth & Hamer (2007) is a discharge that reflects an employer's decision to terminate the employment relationship. Griffith, Hom & Gaertner (2003) reported that involuntary employee turnover includes death, retirement and dismissal. Boxall & Purcell (2007) further explained that turnover initiated by an employee such as resigning to take care of a terminally ill family member should also be considered as involuntary turnover since it involves reasons over which the employee has no control. Carmelli (2003) also defines involuntary turnover as the need to cut costs, downsize or restructure due to reasons which are independent of the affected employee.

The Relationship between Job Rotation and Employee Turnover

A good number of studies have been conducted or carried out on the relationship between job design and employee turnover in the time pasted because, it is not a new concept. A Study conducted by Ajusa and Atambo (2016) at Mount Kenya University revealed that, job rotation has an influence on organizational productivity and employee performance or intentions. Probability sampling design was adopted for the study. The study found or demonstrates that motivation, worker involvement and training and development are antecedents of organizational productivity. Similarly, Adjei (2014) conducted a study on the impact of job rotation on employees' performance a case study: Utrak Financial Services Limited. The study revealed that job rotation is an important programme for allowing employees to acquire new skills, enhance staff productivity, develop new relationships across the company and gain skills needed for future career advancement. Another study conducted by Sharma & Raval (2016), on the impact job enrichment in a Vodafone foam company in Pakistan. The survey also revealed the employee of company complained of lack of responsibility due to job monotony and it affected productivity. The study of Sushi (2014) has revealed that many researchers are of the view that job enrichment and job enlargement have negative effect on work life balance as enlarging and enriching jobs workers tend to work harder and for longer hours. Wandera (2011) however warns that most organizations end up losing the most knowledgeable and effective employees because these employees tend to leave the organization, due to the desire

for permanent work, and for more permanent appointments with other firms that have such vacancies or opening. Previously, organizations were in the habit of providing low stress and less pressure working environments, however that has unfortunately changed. Organizations today have over the last two decades been subjected to many changes, challenges, and problems (Rothmann&Barhuizen, 2008; Coetzee &Rothmann, 2005).

The foregoing argument gave rise to the following hypotheses

Ho₁: There is no significant Relationship between Job rotation and voluntary turnover of food and beverage firms in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Ho₂: There is no significant Relationship between Job rotation and involuntary turnover of food and beverage firms in Rivers State, Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a cross-sectional survey in terms of data generation or collection. The population of this study was drawn from eight food and beverage firms in Rivers state, Nigeria. The population figure one thousand one hundred and twenty (1120) of this study was obtained from the various Human Resource Department of the Food and Beverage Firms. The Taro Yamane (1973) was used to determine the sample size of 295. The structured questionnaire was the primary source of data generation. The reliability test for the instrument was done using the Cronbach Alpha co-efficient and all the items were greater than 0.7 as in table 1 below. The study made use of the Pearson’s Product Moment correlation co-efficient to determine the strength and direction of relationship between the study variables.

Table 1: Reliability Coefficients of variable measures

S/No	Dimensions/Measures of the study variable	Number of items	Number of cases	Cronbach’s Alpha
1	Job Rotation	3	252	0.711
2.	Voluntary Turnover	3	252	0.829
3	Involuntary turnover	3	252	0.715

Source: Research data output, 2019

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The hypotheses were tested using the Pearson’s product moment correlation tool at a 95% confidence interval. Specifically, the tests cover hypotheses Ho₁ to Ho₂ which were bivariate and all stated in the null form. We have relied on the Pearson’s Product Moment (*rho*) statistic to undertake the analysis. The 0.05 significance level is adopted as criterion for the probability of either accepting the null hypotheses at (p>0.05) or rejecting the null hypotheses at (p<0.05).

Table 2: Correlations Matrix for Job Rotation and Employee Turnover

		Job Rotation	Voluntary Turnover	Involuntary Turnover
Job Rotation	Pearson Correlation	1	.762 **	.861 **
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
	N	252	252	252

Voluntary Turnover	Pearson Correlation	.762 **	1	.786 **
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
	N	252	252	252
Involuntary Turnover	Pearson Correlation	.861 **	.786 **	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	252	252	252

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Research Data, 2019 and SPSS output version 23.0

H₀₁: There is no significant Relationship between Job rotation and voluntary turnover of food and beverage firms in Rivers State, Nigeria.

From the result in the table above shows that there is a significant and positive relationship between Job rotation and voluntary turnover. The *rho* value 0.762 indicates this relationship and it is significant at $p\ 0.000 < 0.05$. The correlation coefficient represents a high correlation indicating a strong relationship. Therefore, based on empirical findings the null hypothesis earlier stated is hereby rejected and the alternate upheld. Thus, there is a significant Relationship between Job rotation and voluntary turnover of food and beverage firms in Rivers State, Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant Relationship between Job rotation and involuntary turnover of food and beverage firms in Rivers State, Nigeria.

From the result in the table above shows that there is a significant and positive relationship between Job rotation and involuntary turnover. The *rho* value 0.861 indicates this relationship and it is significant at $p\ 0.000 < 0.05$. The correlation coefficient represents a high correlation indicating a strong relationship. Therefore, based on empirical findings the null hypothesis earlier stated is hereby rejected and the alternate upheld. Thus, there is a significant Relationship between Job rotation and involuntary turnover of food and beverage firms in Rivers State, Nigeria.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This study investigated the relationship between job rotation and employee turnover of food and beverage firms in Rivers State, Nigeria. The findings revealed that a significant relationship between exists between Job Design and Employee Turnover of food and beverage firms Rivers State, Nigeria, Correlation coefficient tool and at a 95% confidence interval. The findings of this study confirmed that job design has an effect on employee turnover of food and beverage firms in Rivers State, Nigeria. The findings of this also corroborated with the survey of Adjei (2014) who conducted a study on the impact of job rotation on employees' performance a case study: Utrak Financial Services Limited. The study revealed that job rotation is an important programme for allowing employees to acquire new skills, enhance staff productivity, develop new relationships across the company and gain skills needed for future career advancement. The study also supported the survey conducted by Sharma & Raval (2016), on the impact job enrichment in a Vodafone company in Pakistan. The survey also revealed the employee of company complained of lack of responsibility due to job monotony and it affected productivity. Thus, the study also affirm the study conducted by Sushi (2014), it has revealed that many researchers are of the view that job enrichment and job enlargement have negative effect on work life balance as enlarging and enriching jobs workers tend to work harder and for longer hours.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Job rotation is a technique which is able to enhance motivation, develop workers' outlook, increase productivity, satisfaction levels and improve organization performance on various levels by its multi-skilled employees. It also provides workers with new opportunities to improve their attitude, thought, capabilities and skills. This study therefore, concludes that Job rotation significantly influences Employee turnover of food and beverage firms in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Therefore, the study recommends that the management of food & beverage firms in Rivers State should ensure that job rotation procedure is applied in such way that will be effective and that employee's should not be rotated in an inappropriate job position.

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